

Lignotrend

LIGNO® Cross Laminated Timber

High-quality timber construction elements for floor, roof and wall structures as well as for use in interior finishing with focus on architectural design, individual configurability and room acoustics.

Highlights of innovative features

- Lignotrend's cross laminated timber CLT components reduce wood consumption by their internal web structure.
- All construction elements are natureplus® certified guaranteeing both high indoor air quality and the fulfilment of all sustainability criteria.
- Lignotrend focuses on providing products with genuine wood surface. A specialty is the locally sourced silver fir which is processed as a knotless surface that allows for unique interior design.

As a pioneer in cross laminated timber, Lignotrend design their products to be individually configured. This allows to meet more typical requirements of building at once than only load-bearing: The products are characterised by intelligent multifunctionality.

Architectural design, sound insulation, room acoustics and increased fire resistance, are examples of disciplines that can be addressed by modification of the elements' internal structure.

Configuration goes with cost-effectiveness for the respective construction task and caters precisely to the planners' specification and design ideas.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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LIGNO TREND®

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